

Constraining the Dynamics and Distances to Intermediate Velocity Clouds Using a 3D Galactic Dust Map

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ABSTRACT

Intermediate velocity clouds (IVCs) are composed of low-density gas in the lower portion of the Galactic halo and move at velocities of 20 to 90 km s⁻¹, anomalous compared to Galactic rotation and typical velocity dispersion. IVCs are thought to be clouds previously ejected from the disk by feedback events, such as supernovae, that are cooling and falling back onto the Galactic disk as part of the Galactic fountain. The release of a high resolution, three-dimensional dust map of the Milky Way from [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) has the potential to constrain the distances to IVCs with lower distance uncertainties than traditional approaches based on UV absorption towards background stars, which are only able to provide an upper limit on the cloud’s distance based on the star’s distance. In this study, we target these potential IVCs detected in the 3D dust map by exploring clouds significantly above and below the Galactic disk ($|z| > 500$ pc) with significant dust densities. We employ a peak finding algorithm on the line-of-sight dust density distribution to constrain the distances to clouds that lie within the boundary of the Edenhofer 3D dust map ($69 \text{ pc} < d < 1.25 \text{ kpc}$) and beyond our Galactic height cut. Using HI 21 cm emission from the HI4PI all-sky survey, we then measure the line-of-sight radial velocity of each distance peak to determine the velocity of each IVC, as well as any velocity gradient across the cloud. By cross-referencing with a study conducted by [Röhser, T. et al. \(2016\)](#), we preliminarily identified five IVCs. Morphological matching between the [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) map and HI4PI survey indicated that all five clouds were good candidates for IVCs. These kinematic constraints provide important inputs for solving the trajectories of the potential IVCs, which will be the subject of future work. These combined spatial and dynamical measurements of a uniform sample of IVCs should help constrain models of inflows/outflows of the Galactic fountain, which plays a key role in the overall galactic baryon cycle of the Galaxy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Intermediate velocity clouds (IVCs) are large structures of Galactic, partially ionized gas traveling at velocities $20 \text{ km s}^{-1} < |v_{lsr}| < 90 \text{ km s}^{-1}$. These clouds travel anomalously compared to Galactic rotation and are typically studied in HI emission or in absorption of ionised gas towards halo stars or quasi-stellar objects ([Marasco et al. 2022](#)). IVCs inform us about the physical structure of the Milky Way Galaxy as they provide information on density and star-forming rates and provide fuel to form new stars in the Milky Way disc ([Planck Collaboration et al. 2011](#); [Lehner et al. 2022](#)). The origins of IVCs are unclear but are thought to be gas produced from feedback events that are cooling and falling back onto the Galactic plane. To better understand the formation and evolution of IVCs, their distances and 3D kinematics must be calculated. The introduction of [Gaia Collaboration et al. \(2018\)](#) helped to place constraints on the once nebulous stellar and dust cloud distances through three-dimensional mapping of dust reddening ([Green et al. 2019](#)). Outside of simulations, the physical structure of individual clouds were only measurable in 3D and before [Green et al. \(2018\)](#), no high resolution (3.4’ to 13.7’) 3D view of clouds was available. New distance constraints on over a billion of stars through parallaxes from Gaia have enabled the construction of new high-resolution 3D dust maps ([Zucker et al. 2021](#)). IVCs generally lie within a distance of $\sim 2 \text{ kpc}$ ([Wakker 2001](#)), however, a limited number of studies have dealt with calculating the distances to these IVCs ([Röhser et al. 2016](#); [Marasco et al. 2022](#); [Smoker et al. 2011](#)). Before Gaia, only upper limits of these distances could be conventionally calculated and now with these parallax measurements, we can calculate the limits on both sides.

[Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) constructed a high-resolution 3D dust map of the spatial distribution of dust extinction. They used the stellar distances and extinction values from [Zhang et al. \(2023\)](#) from Gaia BP/RP spectra. [Zhang et al.](#)

(2023) combined Gaia BP/RP spectra and 2MASS and unWISE infrared photometry to model extinction, distance, and intrinsic parameters of each observed star. In Edenhofer et al. (2023), the authors filter the dataset based on quality and distance to fit the reconstructed volume restricting the Zhang et al. (2023) sample to 53,880,655 stars. In comparison to previous studies, this 3D dust map has more distance bins than Green et al. (2019), contains more homogeneously extended dust clouds than Vergely et al. (2022). It also has a higher dynamic range, less grainy structures, and more compact dust clouds than Leike et al. (2022). This 3D dust map is thus most suitable for IVC mapping due to its parsec-level distance resolution and ability to extend out to large Galactic z-height.

This study utilizes the high resolution Edenhofer et al. (2023) 3D dust map to explore areas of the Milky Way with significant dust densities that could be linked to IVCs. The typical hydrogen gas column density is $N_H \sim 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ (Wakker 2001) with the conversion between column density and extinction values being: $N_H = 2.21 * 10^{21}$ per A(V) mag (Güver & Özel 2009). By using the 3D spatial information in the dust map, distances to each potential IVC can be identified. We then couple the HI emission from HI4PI Collaboration et al. (2016) to calculate the respective velocity of each cloud along a sightline to ensure they fall within the range of IVCs (20 - 90 km s⁻¹). We cross-referenced previous literature velocity values to confirm if each targeted area is a known IVC. The pairing of distances and velocities for each IVC can then be used to provide kinematic constraints to better constrain the inflows and outflows of the Galactic fountain.

2. DATA

2.1. Edenhofer et al. (2023) 3D Dust Map

The Edenhofer et al. (2023) 3D dust map is comprised of 607,125,504 voxels of differential extinction (A(V) per parsec) that are arranged on 516 HEALPix spheres with $N_{side} = 256$ after accounting for the HEALPix cutoffs for < 69 pc and > 1250 pc. The angular resolution is consistent across the map at 14'. The distance resolution varies depending on distance, spanning 1.25 kpc from the Sun with a maximum distance resolution of 0.4 pc at 69 pc and a minimum distance resolution of 7 pc at 1.25 kpc. 3D dust maps typically present either a Cartesian grid reconstruction or spherical grid reconstruction. Cartesian grid reconstructions focus on lessening the “fingers-of-God” effect with the tradeoff of lower angular resolution (Leike & Enßlin 2019; Leike et al. 2020) while spherical grid reconstruction improves angular resolution and covers a larger volume of the Galaxy but has a more pronounced “fingers-of-God” effect (Chen et al. 2019; Green et al. 2019). The Chen et al. (2019) study achieves an angular resolution between 3 and 9' which is significantly smaller than Edenhofer et al. (2023). In a Cartesian coordinate system, physical smoothness priors are used with Gaussian Process priors. However, in a spherical coordinate system, a GP prior is normally too weak to control reconstructions due to the density of voxels depending on distances along the line-of-sight (Green et al. 2019). The Edenhofer et al. (2023) map attains a relatively high angular resolution, falling just behind the angular resolutions of 3D dust reconstructions from Green et al. (2019) at 3.4' and Leike et al. (2022) at 1.9'. It also covers a large Galaxy volume where their method incorporates a Gaussian Processes to smooth out the effects of “fingers-of-God” in a spherical grid. Their method modeled in spherical coordinates with logarithmically spaced voxels in distance to maintain high resolution and distance resolution. We convert the initial spherical coordinates to Cartesian coordinates to determine the height of IVC candidates above the disk in Galactic coordinates. To avoid identifying targets too close to the Galactic plane, we restrict to targets well above and below the Galactic disk with $|z| > 500$ pc. We use this 3D dust map to measure distances to IVC candidates.

2.2. HI4PI: HI Survey

HI4PI (HI4PI Collaboration et al. 2016) is an all-sky survey measuring the emission of Galactic neutral atomic hydrogen (HI), producing spectral-line maps in longitude-latitude-velocity space. The 21-cm line is targeted because it is easily observable in both emission and absorption (Muller & Oort 1951) and has been used to make significant discoveries such as determining that the Milky Way is a spiral galaxy (Oort et al. 1958). HI4PI is comprised of data from the third revision of the Galactic All Sky Survey (GASS) and the Effelsberg-Bonn HI Survey (EBHIS). GASS observations were taken using the 13-beam 21-cm feed array on the 64-m telescope (McClure-Griffiths et al. 2009). EBHIS observations were taken with the seven-beam 21-cm receiver of the Effelsberg 100-m telescope (Wielebinski et al. 2011). Together, the velocity range of the two surveys span $-600 \text{ km s}^{-1} \leq v_{lsr} \leq 600 \text{ km s}^{-1}$ with IVC velocities being well within this range. HI4PI data is used in this study to obtain the velocities of each potential IVC.

3. METHODS

3.1. 3D Projected Dust Map

To identify potential IVCs, we locate regions of significant dust densities with $|z| > 500$ pc in the Galactic Halo. We first converted the pixel coordinates of dust extinction to Galactic coordinates (l, b, d) and then to Cartesian coordinates (x, y, z). IVCs are hypothesized to be falling back onto the Galactic plane so it is important to calculate each IVC's distance away from the Sun and the height in Galactic coordinates. Galactic coordinates provide us with the distance away from the Sun and Cartesian coordinates provide us with the height away from the Galactic plane making both sets of coordinates crucial to have. We take the 3D dust map produced by [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) and integrate it over the distance axis to produce a 3D projected dust map. By visually inspecting the 2D dust extinction map for observable areas of higher dust density, we choose to isolate potential IVCs from typical dust by filtering for areas with $A(V) > 0.035$ mag which is approximately equivalent to a hydrogen column density of $7.73 * 10^{19}$ cm^{-2} when using a gas-to-dust ratio of $N_H = 2.21 * 10^{21}$ per $A(V)$ mag ([Güver & Özel 2009](#)).

Given that we made the $|z| > 500$ cut, each pixel has a corresponding minimum distance based on this criterion. We focus on patches of sky above this z value as matching dust and gas is much harder in the disc. We calculate the minimum distance for each line-of-sight by querying each line of sight along its distance axis and selecting the first distance value such that $|z| > 500$ pc. The minimum distance to the 3D map's maximum distance (1250 pc) provides us with a range of distances for each line-of-sight (l, b). We then query the 3D projected dust map over this range for each sightline to obtain the $A(V)/\text{pc}$ values as a function of distance. We employ a peak-finding algorithm to isolate IVCs to locate regions of higher density than the background for each sightline. The peak-finding algorithm we use is `scipy.find_peaks`. We also apply a smoothing procedure to improve detection of real distance peaks. A Gaussian smoothing parameter is used for the array of extinction values for each sightline with $\sigma = 5$ and then a median moving filter is applied to the Gaussian smoothed data with a window kernel size of 21. The sigma parameter represents the standard deviation of the Gaussian kernel and when applied to smoothing, it determines the extent of smoothing applied to the density estimate while increasing the kernel parameter increases the noise reduction. For the peak-finding algorithm, a prominence parameter of 10^{-5} and a distance parameter of 50 are chosen. The prominence parameter is the minimum vertical distance that needs to be traveled from baseline to peak and the distance parameter is the minimum horizontal distance between neighboring peaks. We choose 10^{-5} for the prominence parameter as any smaller value results in detecting peaks being formed from noise rather than IVCs and we choose 50 for the distance parameter to avoid one distinct peak being considered as multiple. [Figure 1](#) is an example of how the peak finding algorithm detected the distance for each sightline.

Figure 1. Example sightlines of potential IVCs as a function of extinction values versus distances—the peak-finding algorithm was used to find distances for each one. Left (a): Sightline ($l = 142.4^\circ$, $b = 37.8^\circ$) with peak distance at 997 pc. Middle (b): Sightline ($l = -131.4^\circ$, $b = 74.9^\circ$) with peak distance at 785 pc. Right (c): Sightline ($l = -94.8^\circ$, $b = 71.9^\circ$) with peak distance at 744 pc.

3.2. 3D HI Spectral-Line Map

We use the previously identified line-of-sights (l, b) with significant dust densities to extract the spectrum along each one for a single HI4PI pixel from the 3D spectral-line map of [HI4PI Collaboration et al. \(2016\)](#). We employ the same peak-finding algorithm that we used for the peak distances along the spectral axis to determine the velocity at which the clouds in each sightline travel at. The peak-finding algorithm has a prominence parameter of 0.5 and no

Table 1. IVC Measurements

Cloud	l	b	v_{lsr}	Röhser velocity	Distance	Literature distance	Diameter	Known IVC
	(°)	(°)	(km s ⁻¹)	(km s ⁻¹)	(pc)	(pc)	(pc)	
Cloud 1	135.4	53.8	-47.8 ^{+5.35} _{-4.96}	-45	745 ⁺¹² ₋₈	355 ± 95	94.9	IV 21
Cloud 2	149.0	38.4	-52.8 ^{+10.4} _{-7.6}	-54	990 ⁺¹¹⁰ ₋₇₈	900 ± 100	376.6	LLIV Arch
Cloud 3	-103.2	75.4	-32.2 ^{+10.4} _{-23.1}	-30.3	762 ⁺⁹⁷ ₋₂₁₂		551.9	
Cloud 4	-84.8	53.7	-28.2 ^{+12.8} _{-14.2}	-33.7	730 ⁺¹⁰⁶ ₋₁₄₀		481.5	G 283.8+54.9
Cloud 5	-68.8	37.0	30.7 ^{+9.3} _{-17.7}	29	1178 ⁺²⁹ ₋₃₆		57.6	

NOTE—Literature distances and names for cloud 1, cloud 2, and cloud 4 originate from [Hernandez et al. \(2013\)](#), [Wakker \(2001\)](#), and [Magnani & Smith \(2010\)](#), respectively. The literature distance values are upper bounds. The maximum and minimum values for both v_{lsr} and distance are found as the upper and lower limits in their respective columns.

additional smoothing was performed. The default distance parameter of zero is used here as the axis was generally void of noise that could be detected as IVC peaks and actual IVC peaks were generally spaced out. Most sightlines have multiple peaks and the velocity with the highest absolute value is selected in each of those cases (Figure 2). We also limit selected velocities to be $|v_{lsr}| < 90$ km s⁻¹ to ensure they move quickly and fall within the range of IVC velocities.

Figure 2. Example sightlines of potential IVCs as a function of velocities versus HI column density intensity—the peak-finding algorithm was used to find distances for each one. Left (a): Sightline ($l = 142.4^\circ$, $b = 37.8^\circ$) with peak velocity at -46.3 km s⁻¹. Middle (b): Sightline ($l = -131.4^\circ$, $b = 74.9^\circ$) with peak velocity at -39.8 km s⁻¹. Right (c): Sightline ($l = -94.8^\circ$, $b = 71.9^\circ$) with peak velocity at -26.9 km s⁻¹.

4. RESULTS

Out of 786,432 pixels from the [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#), we explore 59,386 pixels of interest to determine if they were IVC candidates. Figure 3a represents the patches of sky with significant dust densities colored by distances. Peak distances increase as $|b|$ decreases. Figure 3b represents the patches of sky with significant dust densities colored by velocities. Most velocities are consistent with falling back onto the Galactic plane.

Of the 7.55% of the sky we searched, we find roughly five features that span distances of 590 to 1207 pc and velocities of -60.4 to 40 km s⁻¹, with mean distances of 745, 990, 762, 730, and 1178 pc and mean velocities of -47.8 , -52.8 , -32.2 , -28.2 , and 30.7 km s⁻¹. To contextualize this with existing studies, we use velocity measurements of potential IVCs from [Röhser et al. \(2016\)](#) which is a study that conducted an all-sky census on Galactic high-latitude molecular clouds moving at intermediate velocities. They targeted HI halo clouds projected to be IVCs to quantify the distribution and amount of gas and ultimately identified 239 IVC candidates. We take the velocity values from the sightlines corresponding to potential IVCs and overlay them on the map with the patches of sky of interest (Figure 4).

Based on correspondence with [Röhser et al. \(2016\)](#), we choose five clouds for further investigation (Figure 5). We compare the morphology of the five clouds between the 3D dust map and the 3D spectral-line map derived using the

Figure 3. Top (a): We peak found distances on the 3D map derived from [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) 3D dust map for distances ranging between 517 and 1244 pc. Bottom (b): Velocities for each sightline found through a peak-finding algorithm for spectral axis from the [HI4PI Collaboration et al. \(2016\)](#) survey ranging between -90 and 90 km s^{-1} .

software `glue` ([Robitaille et al. 2017](#)). The angular resolution of the 3D dust map is $14'$ while the angular resolution of the HI4PI map is slightly lower at $16.1'$. For the 3D dust map, we use the ‘collapse’ feature to extract and take the mean along the distance axis of a given range. Likewise for the 3D spectral-line map, we use the ‘collapse’ feature to extract and analyze a spectrum along the velocity axis by taking the mean of a given range. Collapsing along the distance and velocity axes given a specific range of distances and velocities we select for each IVC allows to visualize the cloud in a lower-dimensional space, the targeted ranges, to identify a pattern. [Figure 5](#) displays the five clouds of interest in both the integrated HI map (left) and the projected 3D dust map (right). The overlaid scatter points are the corresponding [HI4PI Collaboration et al. \(2016\)](#) IVCs.

Table 1 is comprised of the selected clouds and their parameters: Galactic coordinates, velocity, distance, size, and their corresponding literature names and values. To isolate the sightlines that corresponded with each potential IVC, in `glue`, we manually select the area of interest based on visual inspection from [figure 3](#). The software singles out the sightlines with $A(V) > 0.035 \text{ mag}$, allowing us to focus on the IVC. For the upper and lower limits of velocities, we examine the histogram of velocities for each cloud to extract any outliers. To calculate the size of an IVC, each one is visually inspected to see if it is larger longitudinally or latitudinally and from whichever one was larger, the difference

Figure 4. Röhser et al. (2016) velocities overlaid on patches of sky selected for further investigation as potential IVCs.

between the highest and lowest l or b value is used for the angular diameter. We then convert the angular diameter to actual diameter using equation 1, where D is the actual diameter, α is the angular diameter, and d is the distance.

$$D = \frac{\alpha * d}{57.3 \frac{\circ}{\text{radians}}} \quad (1)$$

5. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

By using the three dimension, high resolution Edenhofer et al. (2023) dust map, we can measure distances to intermediate-velocity clouds up to 1.25 kpc from the Sun for the first time. Before the use of 3D dust maps, only upper limits on distances to clouds could be conventionally calculated based on the known distance to a nearby background star. By correlating HI emission from HI4PI Collaboration et al. (2016) with 3D dust maps, we studied the Milky Way’s IVC population that is detected in 3D dust with $|z| > 500$ pc to better understand their spatial and kinematic properties. By cross-referencing velocities of known IVCs from Röhser et al. (2016), we identified five unique IVC candidates—all of which were morphological matches between the 3D integrated HI dust map and projected 3D dust map.

From visual inspection of the 3D spectral line map, the majority of the clouds with integrated extinction values of $A(V) > 0.035$ mag reside in the northern hemisphere with negative v_{lsr} . All five IVC candidates of this study were in the Northern hemisphere. The velocities measured by Röhser et al. (2016) along sightlines intersecting the IVC candidates match well with all five clouds. We were only able to find previously calculated distances of clouds 1 and 2 from existing studies (Hernandez et al. 2013; Wakker 2001). Distances for cloud 2 match well with the Wakker (2001) study, however, cloud 1 has a clear discrepancy with the Wakker (2001) values. The literature distance values do not make the $|z| > 500$ pc cut, therefore, would fall below the minimum distance for the sightlines associated with this IVC. We further explored if there were multiple peak distances in extinction values for this IVC beyond the minimum distance (Figure 7). We found a peak at 297 pc which falls within the range from the literature values. The Hernandez et al. (2013) study detected this IVC using Na I absorption of two nearby stars, HD101714 ($l = 135.93^\circ$, $b = 52.78^\circ$) and HD101075 ($l = 135.49^\circ$, $b = 51.13^\circ$). Given that only two stars were observed, it is possible that the entire cloud was not sampled as the stars located at roughly the same sightline. For clouds 3 and 4, when choosing the ranges of velocities to collapse over, their velocities spanned over 100 km s^{-1} which was too large of a range. In both cases, there were two distinct Gaussian peaks within this range, so, we refined their ranges to 33.5 km s^{-1} and 27 km s^{-1} , respectively.

Our approach for measuring the distances has several limitations. Given that we only thoroughly investigated pixels with $|z| > 500$ pc and $A(V) > 0.035$ mag, we may have potentially missed IVCs located at a lower height and with smaller extinction values. We also only focused on comparing the sightline HI velocities of potential IVCs from one study which could have hindered our potential to identify more than five clouds.

Figure 5. Left (a): Integrated HI column density map for all five clouds, one through five shown from top to bottom. Right (b): Projected 3D dust map from [Edenhofer et al. \(2023\)](#) for all five clouds, one through five shown from top to bottom. All five clouds have morphologies matching across the HI column density map and 3D dust map suggesting the HI and dust maps were correctly matched. The overlaying scatter points are the sightlines of the potential IVCs identified in [Röhser et al. \(2016\)](#).

Figure 6. The five IVCs plotted in 3D in Cartesian coordinates, colored by their velocities found using HI4PI.

Figure 7. Sightline from cloud 1 ($l = 136.25^\circ$, $b = 50.38^\circ$) extending back to 200 pc. A peak at 297 pc is found, falling within the distance range found in [Hernandez et al. \(2013\)](#).

Using these kinematic constraints, future studies will be able to model these IVCs and calculate their trajectories. This will help to better understand how IVCs contribute to the inflows and outflows of the Galactic fountain and understand the vertical density structure of the interstellar medium. [Marasco et al. \(2022\)](#) previously modeled the trajectory of IVCs and high-velocity clouds using the absorption towards 55 Galactic halo stars. They found that features associated with the inflow tend to be diffused across the sky while features associated with the outflow are more confined to two opposing directions ($l = -140^\circ$, $b = 40^\circ$) and ($l = 40^\circ$, $b = -40^\circ$). Using the distances from 3D dust maps to these IVCs, we can continue to constrain the trajectory of these clouds, depending on their location in the sky, and understand the cause of the distinction between dispersion from the inflow and outflow. These models

can ultimately help to map out the galactic baryon cycle of the Milky Way to understand the star formation history of the Galaxy.

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